

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM SUPPLY CHAIN AND ICT ROLE IN SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION HOSIPITALITY.

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Tourism supply chain involves package in several services: 1. Travel agencies operators' e-tourism, to finalize tourism. 2. Finalize tourism package, transport, and accommodation, hotel industry which includes catering, food beverage, leisure services, sports activities, and health services. The co-operation of network inside supply chain can represent a competitive advantage to small tour operators, wherein are more sensitive to competition, in tourism supply chain. The correlation between tourism, and sustainability, of tourism industry is the attraction, competition of each of the organization with tourism industry in supply chain. Tourism is multi-segment industry, where products are consumed on the spot. Tourism industry is also fragmented industry, with high complexity, due to price sensitiveness nature, of demand and the perishability, intangibility, in the tourism industry in supply chain. Tourism like all other business in supply chain operates through B2B relationship, and can delivery, sustainability performance improvement through good financial performance of the tourism industry, by working to improve the business operation of each supplier in supply chain. The difference in tourism supply chain is that tourist are in demand, with the product demand, and the product they procure, which are of high service requirement in higher proportion , and which requires prompt or immediate production to enjoy the holiday preference. The most important distribution system applied in tourism supply chain; 1. One stage: from a primary supplier of services to a consumer through reservation, either directly to travelers. 2. Two stage: where the system involves any middle man or an agent to do the work. In tourism industry distribution strategy has an impact on development, and it is essential to channel the distribution in an appropriate form the beginning to end to end in supply chain tourism.

Concept of tourism in supply chain: Tourism supply chain industry comprises of suppliers, operators, tourists and other organizations, and tourism supply chain, purchasing various resources, and they transferring them to services, and support which finally goes into the hands of the tourists.

Supply chain tourism is also determined by comprehensive products travel industry in supply chain which necessarily cannot supply all the services required in coordination with relevant tourism aspects in supply chain.

Features: Supply chain as compared to traditional manufacturing industry, supply chain tourism is characterized by high complexities, risk, and very important is the quality control aspect in supply chain tourism, complexity of the tourism products, also leading to complexity of the tourism leading to complicated process in supply chain tourism.

The requirement of high quality coordination allocation, and a reasonable resource allocation, and if uncontrollable a good quality of service may not be admissible in catering, accommodation, good transportation, supplier efficiency, which are the aspects that face challenges, and it is necessary for the travel enterprises to coordinate any semi-finished product, necessary for tourist in supply chain, and control product quality.

Problems faced by supply chain in tourism: Tourism is basically to satisfy the needs of the tourist, either domestic or internationally, however the allocation of the needs is to be optimized. Tourism do lack any special innovation in supply chain, which is caused by intensive market competition, in the field of supply chain. Any depth of tourism experimental ideas, and supplies pertaining a high class content, becomes insufficient.

Tourism in supply chain has also given preference to individual travelers, with relevant information on arranging of trips, having made through Internet of Things facilities.

Based on supply chain tourism many scenic spots have come back on competitive terms, and this way of marketing, and reception centre, has made e-commerce to get in touch with tourists in supply chain, with reference to accommodation, catering, and entertainment.

In this junction many travel enterprises are gradually losing their positions of their potential in the market, hence a diversified tourism supply chain has been adopted to personalize tourists in supply chain.

In the tourism supply chain travel enterprises are provided with risk which are complicated, as they are unable to respond to the market changes in tourism supply chain, and this has led to changes in supply chain, and this consequences has led to short term benefits, thus ignoring the scenic spots, which result in damages to environment, and that have no influence in tourist in supply chain.

In order to bring in sustainable tourism in supply chain, is that planning should be developed to manage tourism activities from a perspective point, in the long run, and on the other hand reduce the damaged caused to tourism, on travelling, like maintaining the ecological balance of tourism, industry, and protection, development of tourist sports, in supply chain, in order to improve the quality and economy of the country in supply chain.

Tourism in supply chain should have the responsibility to protect culture, environment scene, water sports activities, and medical programs, thus reduce damage to environment, and chose low carbon transportation, E-commerce tourism.

Platform to develop mobile App, which has changed the way to obtain information, and delivery, results in supply chain. Tourism development in supply chain has realized the time and space, limitation, and traveler can deal with suppliers and other information directly. Tourism development in supply chain is collectively analyzing travel information that should be beneficial to make quick decision, and improve products and services.

Green Tourism in Supply chain: Supply chain is given prominence and priority in the development of green tourism, and requires to examine, and evaluate various manufacturing organization to make, and source to disposal that can be coordinated, and controlled as green supply chain, in the design, manufacturing, maintenance, marketing, and consumption of products in tourism supply chain.

Inventory strategy in supply chain tourism: The most important strategy is the inventory classification that attracts tourism is the activities that coincide with accommodation, transportation, that are necessary to match with an understanding or visitors demand, satisfaction, destination, and ensure that the expectations are met.

Customer service strategy in supply chain tourism: providing accommodation, flight details, and a attraction of tourist destination, which are an vital part of the tourism industry in supply chain.

Customer satisfaction integration: supply chain integration that links all the entities in supply chain preferably manufacturing, suppliers, distribution, customers, cooperation, to form a supply chain, and develop products into a single organization with greater integration process in tourism supply chain.

Sustainable in tourism business can also develop the existing business in tourism, and attract view in business, opportunity in supply chain, and increase the revenue in supply chain, as it also contributes to the reputation of the organization operating the supply chain. The supply chain that contribute with quality to improve, and to provide better customer service, with contribution to increase customer satisfaction, strength, bring in value enhance publicity, and marketing tourism opportunities and have better acceptance in supply chain.

Sustainable supply chain management is the trend to use the policies of purchase, and the practices to facilitate sustainable development at the tourist destination. Research on environmental aspects of manufacturing, while other aspects of sustainability, or the challenges for service sector are largely ignored, but sustainable supply chain has given to the important tour operators, as the product depends on the activities of suppliers, such as providing accommodation, transportation, and relevant activities that form an important part of the contribution to a sustainable tourism, which will be more effective through responsibility for the which the impact of the supplier is important in supply chain.

Supply chain comprises the suppliers of all the goods and services, that go into the delivery of tourism, which the products to the consumer, but also to maintain the harmony among the different aspects, which affects largely the satisfaction of the tourist in the tourism industry. If the tourists become satisfied and contented, they will come again, and it is liable to increase the revenue, which can be distributed, so the prime concern of the tourism and supply chain is necessarily satisfied with guests being given importance, and thus earn profit.

Main parties involved in supply chain are the providers of accommodation, transporters, and the activities handlers in their day to day functions in tourism, which involves also the food supply, and the operations of supply which operates in B2B relationship, and that the supply chain is able to deliver a sustainable performances, along with the financial planning performances by working on improved business, so that each supplier benefits by the life cycle.

The main difference between tourism supply chain and other sectors is that tourist travels to the product, and the product they buy have a particular high performance and service, as it involves the higher proportion of people involvement, in the production for which a holiday experience at a sustainable supply chain is envisaged. Tourism management is a sustainable management and cannot be diminished.

Tourism and hospitality industry are mainly developed, influenced by the size of information, and the digital technology usage in an environment. The growth of information and communication technology has become an integral part of the hospitality industry. The use and spread of information and communication technology has brought in a great potential to accelerate growth in tourism and hospitality, and in the process human resources has been developed, by reducing the regulatory network in the development of tourism and hospitality industry, thus increasing the knowledge.

Information and communication technology offers good innovative ideas to cities embedded around with good buildings; good water management systems, excellent road/rail transportation (metro rail) developed in big cities, efficiency in energy system (solar/wind/thermal) power, and thus reduce waste management.

Information and communication technology innovation application offers good transport, manufacturing, agriculture, urban development, which help to bring in the climate change, and it optimizes value chain, in supply chain, by reduction in cost, resource usage, and emissions, thus providing resilience to climate adaption, with launching of space programs, bringing in real timely climate and weather information.

Information and communication technology, manages crisis management, disruption, and has the means of implementing of a consumption pattern by the use of data, which increases transparency, and which empowers the economic development.

Information and communication technology, implements good partnership in most global manufacturing industries promoting technology, building capacity in production, improving hospitality, by enabling data build up and having accountability to the cost.

Sustainable development is so much in focus on the global warming and climate change, and also continuous depletion of natural resources. Implementation of sustainable consumption and production pattern is going on to achieve a sustainable development in tourism and hospitality industries. The growth of industrialization is making developing countries more susceptible to unsustainable pattern of production and consumption.

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